

Smart Energy Services to Improve the Energy Efficiency of the European Building Stock

Deliverable n°:	D8.2
Deliverable name:	Consolidated Services and Technical Standards Catalogue
Version:	1
Release date:	31/03/2022
Dissemination level:	Public
Status:	Final
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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 847066.

Document history:

Version	Date of issue	Content and changes	Edited by
0.1	20/04/2021	First draft version	OFFIS
0.2	30.06.2021	Consolidated second draft version, added content and summaries	OFFIS, (Uslar)
0.5	30.10.2021	Added feedback from ADV, added relation to p4P and project content in more detail	ADV, OFFIS
0.9	14.2.2022	Review and changes	OFFIS
1	222.03.2022	Final version	OFFIS, Copyedit-Team

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Deliverable beneficiaries:

WP / Task
WP6 – P4P schemes to engage third party investors in energy efficiency
T7.3 – Define the data models and service interfaces for the smart services
T8.3 – Governance models as risk and opportunity

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

Acronym	Description
BACS	Building Automation and Control System
BEMS	Building Energy Management System
CIM	Common Information Model
DR	Demand Response
DSM	Demand Side Management
EE	Energy Efficiency
EEM	Energy Efficiency Measure
OC	Occupancy Comfort
P4P	Pay for Performance
SBT	Smart Building Technology
SRI	Smart Readiness Indicator for Buildings
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
WP	Work Package

Executive summary

Within this deliverable from the SENSEI project, an overview of meaningful ‘smart’ technologies in the context of buildings is given in a so-called service catalogue acting as a single source for an overview of technologies in the context of smart buildings actively contributing to the KPI of a Smart Readiness Indicator. Within SENSEI, those services are used in the context of the P4P – Pay for Performance scheme to evaluate if certain services are more beneficial than others in another context than the original indicator. The services are characterized by their scope of a domain, their current market share on pre-existing conditions. These conditions cover mostly technology which has to be in place in order as enabler for further technologies. Services are defined and put in context with simulations and calculations with documented adjustments to the original developed SRI. Taking these adjustments into account, the impact evaluation consists of separately simulating respective calculating the changes to the building properties achieved by a P4P program in conjunction with the individual Smart Building Technologies (SBT) groups, and assess the resulting Smart Readiness Indicator. The difference between the SRI value after the basic P4P program and the new value constitute a quantified impact evaluation rate of the associated SBT group, which can be evaluated and compared to those obtained by other groups of SBT.

The results documented in the deliverable present a meaningful set of technologies from the SRI, assess them for certain benefits in combinations of them being deployed and, thus, giving information to the potential occupants and retrofitters of buildings.

1 Introduction

The eighth work package of the SENSEI project is titled “*The future of P4P in the market*”. Its scope encompasses external factors and predictions for future developments to be taken into consideration during the design of the scope of the SENSEI Pay for Performance (P4P) model. The first task in this scope in SENSEI identified current policies and regulations within the EU as potential risk factors or opportunities for the proposed P4P schemes. Specific arrangements for the governance of these schemes will be devised through stakeholder engagement with the knowledge obtained in previous tasks of the WP in order to increase the schemes’ acceptance by consumers.

This deliverable presents and reviews so called ‘Smart’ Building Technologies (SBT) as candidates for inclusion into P4P schemes after the SENSEI model. Notice that, however, smart does not necessarily mean energy efficient or high or any carbon dioxide reduction. Also, active ambient lighting can improve the occupants’ life quality and though it might need additional electric energy. Advanced systems and installations in a building can support and enhance the measures of a (P4P) scheme for greater energy efficiency, flexibility and data exploitation by all involved parties, thus, realizing a Win-Win situation. Suitable candidates of technologies were critically investigated and analysed regarding their current technological readiness, market share as well as legal and financial restrictions within the EU.

The associated technical standards were catalogued in order to facilitate the incorporation into P4P plans in future tasks of SENSEI. The final recommendations factors in quantitative assessments of the technologies’ P4P synergy potential by utilizing the Smart Readiness Indicator (SRI) methodology.

A test pipeline will be developed to evaluate the impact on P4P schemes for the pilot buildings selected in the project. The P4P plans this task aims to support will be derived in a later work package based on surveys conducted in SENSEI and extended to engage third party investors.. This task will be able to provide feedback to this work and address uncertainties about technological readiness and interoperability therein. The determined requirements for each technology to enable data transfer to the energy efficiency aggregator will be passed to the step where they can be taken into consideration when designing the aggregator’s service interface – optimizing the interface and API for the services which are most beneficial and part of the SRI leading to a synergy when being implemented.

3 Smart Building Technologies in the SENSEI project context

A Smart Building Technology (SBT) is an installation and technological instance that enhances a building's service portfolio through facilitating flexible and (more) efficient functionalities. The 'smartness' is referring to the automation or digital interconnection of devices within the building perimeter.

So called 'Hardware' SBT increase the capacity of the building faculties and are often a precondition for installing the so called 'Software' SBT that provide operational capability and are often deployed on top of the 'Hardware'. The smartness of buildings has as of now become integral to the sustainability of buildings in regards of energy efficiency (EE) and climate impact from the view of the Commission. The EU stated 'smart homes' as one of its ten central action areas for strategic investment policies in energy [1]. For a member country like Germany, residential and commercial buildings make up for an emission of carbon dioxide for up to 30 per cent, outlining the potential for the building as a driver to stop climate change.

Within the SENSEI project, technology candidates were collected from energy efficiency program analyses performed in the work package WP4, the guidelines to P4P programs developed in task T5.2, and the consultation of involved experts. Additional technologies were extracted from the Energy Efficiency Measures (EEMs) of the SHERPA reports for the pilot buildings selected in task T5.1. The list was completed by consultation of external partner projects and independent research. The relevant data investigated for each technology resolved around its potential value to a P4P program, its technological readiness and so called deployability in buildings among others. Thus, the technologies chosen provide a proper selection of state-of-the art in science and industry.

An internal review determined the most promising and viable candidates from this list. These SBT underwent further and more thorough research into their market share, migration paths, as well as connected cost factors and legal restrictions imposed on them within the EU.

The following two tables provide an overview and short profiles of the selected technologies. Table 1 is dedicated towards governing systems and system functionalities to be used in the context of smart buildings. Besides the header, there are five main fields for each entry, which aim to answer the respective questions briefly as follows:

- What is this technology installed for and how does it fulfil its purpose? What data is collected?
- How would the adaption of this technology add to a P4P plan and its goals?
- How deployable/ mature is this technology? Is it broadly accepted within the EU market? What are its market share?
- What other technologies have to already exist in the building or be installed beforehand?
- Does this technology have significant expenses for its installation or maintenance? Are there regulatory respective legal or interoperability restrictions on its usage? Does it only apply to buildings of a certain type/ occupancy profile?

Designation	Building Automation and Control System (BACS)
Brief description	The BACS interconnects and coordinates the control subsystems for the various domains and installations. All collected sensor data is displayed and visualised via a user interface where the desired target values can be set.
Synergy potential (to EE specifications / P4P plans)	The coordination of already existing subsystems is highly cost effective. A centralized control system is also often a requirement for participation in market oriented portfolios and energy service development (ESCOs, EPC-contracts etc.).
EU market share & technological readiness	Annual growth forecasts for the period of 2019-2024 range from 3.1 % to 4.8 %. About 50 % of new buildings link HVAC with other building services, but 75 % -- 90 % of overall building operation software sold remains server-based [2].
Required technologies	Domain specific subsystems and connected sensors, auxiliary systems (fault detection, performance evaluation etc.)
Significant cost factors & restrictions (if any)	The data of the various subsystems has to be processed to a uniform presentation. The BACS has to be capable of two-way communication with all its subsystems.
Designation	Building Energy Management System (BEMS)
Brief description	The BEMS aggregates and regulates the building's energy consumption rates. The user can closely monitor and adjust controllable subsystems through this common interface.
Synergy potential (to EE specifications / P4P plans)	The monitoring of the separate energy consumption domains eases the settlement of EE programs without conflict to the electrification of space/water heating systems. The subsystems can incorporate the methods for the dynamic M&V of energy savings proposed in <i>D7.1 Methods for the dynamic M&V of energy savings</i> ²
EU market share & technological readiness	The annual growth for the 2015-2020 period was around 22.48 % [3]. BEMS are commonly used for HVAC systems, lighting systems and asset performance optimization among others.
Required technologies	Energy meters, value actuators, interoperable subsystems of energy consuming/producing installations
Significant cost factors & restrictions (if any)	The only variable cost factor is the installation of new interfaces for interoperability with the existing subsystems.
Designation	DHW storage management system
Brief description	The storage management system handles the charge, release and distribution for its connected DHW storage reservoir according to external signals. It can gather and relay relevant status information about the storage, such as capacity, release rate, operability, temperature etc.

² <https://zenodo.org/record/4695123#.YkVoYo9ByMp>

Synergy potential (to EE specifications / P4P plans)	Scheduled pre-heating can relieve the grid during peak times.
EU market share & technological readiness	DHW storage management systems are already widely used.
Required technologies	Thermostats
Significant cost factors & restrictions (if any)	Storage technologies are not in the focus of SENSEI.
Designation	Adaptive systems for controllable consumption devices
Brief description	A control system or aggregator can regulate the consumption rate of controllable devices in the building remotely. This enables Demand Side Management (DSM) for Demand Response (DR) or Smart Grid integration, and can be provided via a service platform. Candidate devices are electric vehicles, heat pumps, night storage heaters and electric energy storages among others.
Synergy potential (to EE specifications / P4P plans)	Controllable equipment lets building owners benefit from DR service tariffs and makes the demand prediction more resilient. Energy savings accumulated by EE improvements can be stored for later release during peak times, relieving the grid. The control systems can target deep energy retrofits.
EU market share & technological readiness	Most controllable consumption devices provide a separate management system.
Required technologies	Advanced control system (e.g., BACS/BEMS), controllable consumption devices (including batteries, TES)
Significant cost factors & restrictions (if any)	SENSEI focusses on EE, but can utilize synergies with DR. Controllable consumption devices can be expensive in their installation.
Designation	Ventilation control system
Brief description	The room humidity and temperature are measured through air quality sensors. The ventilation activity is automatically regulated to meet the adjustable set points. An automated schedule profits from night/free cooling and H,x-directed control.
Synergy potential (to EE specifications / P4P plans)	Energy consumption at peak times can be reduced.
EU market share & technological readiness	The indoor air quality monitoring market is forecast to grow over 8 % over the 2021–2025 period [4].
Required technologies	Air quality and presence sensors, HVAC

Significant cost factors & restrictions (if any)	Retroactive HVAC system installation is expensive and scales with the building size.
Designation	Window control system
Brief description	Based on sunlight incidence determined by light sensors, or following a predefined schedule, insulated windows with varying spectral properties or moveable shades can automatically reduce exposition to heat radiation at peak times.
Synergy potential (to EE specifications / P4P plans)	Advanced window control systems effectively lower the energy consumption for cooling and can be coordinated with ventilation and heating systems through a BACS.
EU market share & technological readiness	For the 2018-2024 period, the market is forecast to grow at an annual rate of about 6 % due to the increasing implementation of these systems in the health care sector [5].
Required technologies	Insulated windows with varying spectral properties, moveable shades, light sensors, microprocessors
Significant cost factors & restrictions (if any)	As a separate installation would be costly, this upgrade is most suited for combination with a general modernization of windows, or for otherwise inaccessible windows.
Designation	Participation in Smart Building communities or cooperation models
Brief description	The data BACSS and BEMSs aggregate can be shared between cooperating buildings to identify opportunities to participate in energy saving portfolios and evaluate EEM plans. The energy management these control systems provide further enable the provision of EE as a demand-side resource.
Synergy potential (to EE specifications / P4P plans)	Management systems can share their accumulated data with big data collectors both as a business model to compensate for diminishing sales of energy, and for participation in social policies (e.g., addressing energy poverty). Communication interfaces also facilitate the use of EE as a demand-side grid resource / network service (e.g., avoiding congestion), or as a demand-side energy resource for the power system (e.g., investment by third parties in EE auctions).
EU market share & technological readiness	The implementation as a network service to the power system is currently deemed to have the greatest chance to be operational in the EU as the expected guarantees required from the grid operator may be less stringent, compared to capacity and data auctions.
Required technologies	Advanced control system (e.g., BACS/BEMS)
Significant cost factors & restrictions (if any)	The energy market legislation is very restrictive in regards to demand-side energy resource provision. The P4P offer is probably not sufficiently robust yet to contractually guarantee a certain capacity.
Designation	Automated lighting system

Brief description	The lighting system can be equipped with presence and sunlight sensors to automatically adjust the local artificial lighting to the presence of occupants and natural light respectively. In addition, the system can incorporate adjustable lighting schedules.
Synergy potential (to EE specifications / P4P plans)	This energy measure can easily be incorporated into long-ranging P4P plans.
EU market share & technological readiness	The Smart Lighting Market was over USD 2 billion in 2017 and is expected to exhibit a robust annual growth of around 20 % between 2018 and 2024. Europe holds the highest share in the smart lighting market worldwide [6].
Required technologies	Sensors (motion, light)
Significant cost factors & restrictions (if any)	New outlets in places which have not been covered before

Table 1: 'Software' upgrades

The technical installations in Table 2 are required/desirable for some of the systems in the table above (viable pre-conditions) , and/or are easily incorporable into P4P plans to achieve further alignment with the EE specifications. They are grouped by domain or functionality as those have increased likelihood of being applicable to the same P4P programs.

Most of them are widely used, with their importance mostly depending on building region (member country) and type (commercial /residential). Minor overlaps between the packages might occur but are not detrimental to the selection process.

Category	Description
Local energy generation	The inclusion of local energy generation (e.g., photovoltaic panels, (micro) wind turbines) and energy saving converters (e.g., thermal solar modules for DHW) can steer a program towards the goal of decarbonizing the power system. Renewable energy generation is, however, not at the centre of SENSEI.
Domain interlock	Heating, Ventilation, and Air Conditioning (HVAC) systems coordinate the building’s installations in these domains to achieve a high indoor air quality and thermal comfort. They are well established in the industry. A Thermally Activated Building Structure (TABS) utilises the mass of a building as a buffer to the changing cooling or heating loads over the course of a day. The temperature of the slabs can be influenced by running cold or hot water through interior pipes.
Heat efficient technologies	Modern ventilation systems with installed waste heat recovery and filter technology can deliver potential energy savings of up to 20 percent. Heat exchange systems can facilitate the redirection of surplus heat to connected building blocks. In the same vein, room specific heating and automatic door closers avoid unnecessary and costly overproduction of heat for large buildings with inconsistent occupancy profiles.
Efficient lighting technologies	LEDs can achieve electricity savings of up to 80 percent compared to incandescent lamps and do not require a warm-up time before they reach full brightness as compact fluorescent lamps do. Light deflectors (e.g., mirrors) allow to “pipe” the light falling on the roof or on a wall-mounted collector to more interior spaces of the building.
Restorations	Replacing outdated facilities with energy use certified equipment is the most basic way of improving a building’s EE and avoiding environmental compliance costs.
Thermal insulation	Modern windows stabilize the temperature by having a layer of gas between panes of glass act as thermal insulation. Their airtight installation can also significantly reduce the heat loss within the building envelope, while barely visible coatings on the glass reflect long-waved heat radiation. Plastic spacers have less thermal conductivity than traditional aluminium spacers. Sun protections such as window facades and solar films can provide further relieve to the cooling system.
Metering devices	Metering systems record information about the consumption, voltage level, current or similar properties of a building’s installations or accumulate them for an entire building in near-real time. Smart Meters are capable of displaying these data and communicating

	with the consumer and the supplier in either direction. Thus they can greatly contribute to awareness in consumption as well as to monitoring and billing arrangements.
Controllable consumption devices	Devices that can be controlled remotely in their consumption/release profile through metering systems can contribute to DR services and peak load reduction. This category comprises electric vehicle chargers, heat pumps, night storage heaters and electric energy storages among others.
Frequency converters	Frequency converters can be used in the engineering building systems to optimize the operation of fans, pumps, and other relevant equipment.
Energy retrofiting technologies	Thermal Energy Storage (TES) reduces the energy consumption for heating/cooling during peak climatic conditions and makes energy savings more impactful by providing storage capacities. Geothermal heat pumps access the heat stored beneath a building to condition its interior. Rotary heat wheels and heat pipes can manage to recover 50-80 % of heat energy for redeploy in ventilation temperature regulation. Desiccant-based cooling systems for buildings with high occupancy profiles such as hospitals, supermarkets or apartment buildings can take up large dehumidification loads over long periods of time.

Table 2: 'Hardware' upgrades for buildings

4 P4P synergy evaluation and calculation

4.1 Methodology

The Smart Readiness Indicator from the EC constitutes a methodology to score the so called operational potential of a building. The calculated percentage value reflects the building's overall potential(!) capability to exploit the present installations and equipment. The SRI constitutes of several sub scores to inform on the building's strong and weak suits.

The final score is calculated as a weighted average of three impact categories covering Energy Efficiency (EE), Occupant Comfort (OC) and Demand Response (DR) respectively.

These categories are further divided into impact criteria: energy savings and maintenance & fault prediction for EE, comfort, convenience and information to occupants for OC, and energy flexibility & storage for DR. Each criterion score is averaged from sub scores in the nine domains heating, domestic hot water cooling, ventilation, lighting, electricity, electric vehicles, dynamic envelope and monitoring & control. For the EE and DR criteria, these domain scores are weighted according to their energy consumption share, while the OC weights are fixed as there is no direct correlation between consumption and comfort. A more detailed description of the SRI computation structure and guides to its interpretation can be found in D5.1² of SENSEI (titled *Selected buildings, SRI and comfort assessments*, prepared by OFFIS).

The P4P synergy evaluation is based on changes to the SRI values of demonstration buildings as the P4P program progresses with different groups of SBTs. First, the as-is status of a demonstration building is determined. Candidates for demonstration buildings of various types were collected and described in greater detail in D5.1³.

From this building data, a standard non-smart building was derived as well. This standard candidate was designed so that all the SBT listed in the previous chapter are not pre-installed but applicable, providing a direct measure of comparison to all SBTs.

³ The deliverable is marked as confidential and not publicly available

As a second step, a P4P program without any of the SBTs is simulated on the demonstration building and its SRI score re-assessed. This new score serves as the baseline for subsequent SBT supported programs to compare to.

Importantly, the SRI was primarily designed to inform on the unexplored potential of a building's already present equipment – the often called low hanging fruits. In order to repurpose it as a comparison framework, some adjustments to the regular assessment process are necessary.

Obstacle 1: Only the services of installed technologies contribute to the calculation. As a result, the SRI score might decrease after equipping the building with new technologies that have a high point ceiling. The unlocking of new potential utilizing additional functionalities should not be penalized.

Solution 1: All technologies of interest to the comparison are fixed in their deployment from the start. The baseline assessment of the building already includes the associated services at the lowest, non-smart level even if the building lacks the required equipment at the moment of the calculation run. This way, the simulated installation of these technologies becomes proportional to the changes in SRI scoring after re-assessment.

Obstacle 2: Improvements to the EE of an energy domain within the building reduce that domain's consumption share and therefore its weighting in parts of subsequent SRI calculations. If this domain performed considerably better than the others, the overall SRI score might plummet despite direct improvements to the smartness of individual services.

Solution 2: The original energy distribution of the domains is fixed and not adjusted to the possible redistributions of subsequent simulations. Consequently, improvements to energy usage related services are guaranteed to benefit the buildings' SRI score.

Obstacle 3: Conversely, new installations with high energy consumption or production raise the importance of a smart governance for their domain. As this potential is not represented in the baseline SRI score, technological upgrades might be discouraged if the domains smartness is below average for the building.

Solution 3: The increases in energy consumption/production are factored into the fixed energy distribution used for all assessments within the ongoing comparison run. The potential the other SBT groups have to offer will, thus, be represented in all assessments, supporting the comparability of the different test results.

Taking these adjustments into account, the third step of the impact evaluation consists of separately simulating/ calculating the changes to the building properties achieved by the P4P program in conjunction with the individual SBT groups, and assess the resulting smart readiness. The difference between the SRI value after the basic P4P program and these new values constitute a quantified impact evaluation rate of the associated SBT group, which can be evaluated and compared to those obtained by other groups of SBTs.

For P4P programs evolving around a select few building aspects, it might prove more valuable to directly compare specific sub-scores of the SRI rather than their weighted average represented by the final scoring.

All SRI assessments were conducted on the advanced evaluation level, as many of the involved technologies are not considered for base level SRI assessments.

4.2 Results

In order to obtain noticeable scoring impacts, the SBTs have to be sorted into test groups.

The smallest units of this separation were built by associating Software upgrades with their required and exploited Hardware upgrades, as depicted in Table 3.

Building the units around the Software upgrades suits the structure and design intent of the SRI quite well, which will lead to more stable and reliable testing results. A test group can consist of any number of these units. Single-unit test groups serve the evaluation of a particular SBT, while multi-unit test groups respect the dependency on subsystems and highlight the synergies between the SBTs.

They are labelled in Table 4. In both tables, full/partial inclusion of a particular element is marked by green/yellow colouring legend.

Hardware SBTs	Local energy generation	Domain interlock	Heat efficient technologies	Efficient lighting technologies	Restorations	Thermal insulation	Metering devices	Controllable consumption devices	Frequency converters	Energy retrofitting technologies
Software SBTs										
BACS										
BEMS										
DHW storage management system										
Adaptive systems for controllable consumption devices										
Ventilation control system										
Window control system										
Participation in Smart Building communities or cooperation models										
Automated lighting system										

Table 3: Assignment of Hardware SBT to Software SBT units

	SBT groups												
	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M
BACS													
BEMS													
DHW storage management system													
Adaptive systems for controllable consumption devices													
Ventilation control system													
Window control system													
Participation in Smart Building communities or cooperation models													
Automated lighting system													
Additional measures													
SRI scoring increase compared to unsupported P4P	3%	3%	4%	6%	19%	19%	24%	31%	42%	48%	51%	58%	66%

Table 4: SBT testing group compositions

To gain a point of comparison, the SRI score of the demonstration buildings before and after a P4P project without synergic technologies was determined beforehand (see Table 5).

The pilot building scores are based on the assessments conducted in D5.1, with the adjustments described in the methodology of this chapter. The standard non-smart building was determined by simulation at an SRI score of around 5 %, which a standard P4P program can increase to around 34 %.

Building ID	Function	SRI score before P4P	SRI score after P4P without SBTs
CU01	Restoration Centre	21%	34%
CU02	Museum	42%	54%
ED60	Public School	35%	45%
OF27	Courthouse	22%	37%
OF39	Courthouse	40%	52%
OF40	Courthouse	33%	44%
OT36	Penitentiary Centre	20%	37%
OT37	Penitentiary Centre	18%	37%
OT38	Penitentiary Centre	11%	35%
MO01	Simulation	5%	34%

Table 5: Baseline SRI scores of demonstration buildings

The following table depicts the scoring changes for P4P programs supplemented with the various aforementioned SBT groups A to M.

Building ID	SBT group												
	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M
CU01	1%	3%	4%	6%	23%	23%	29%	33%	38%	41%	59%	63%	66%
CU02	1%	4%	4%	6%	18%	13%	15%	36%	25%	28%	40%	43%	46%
ED60	2%	4%	4%	6%	26%	10%	18%	34%	27%	30%	48%	52%	55%
OF27	2%	3%	4%	5%	17%	27%	36%	32%	45%	50%	59%	62%	63%
OF39	2%	4%	4%	5%	17%	6%	17%	32%	26%	30%	42%	45%	48%
OF40	2%	3%	4%	6%	15%	20%	26%	27%	39%	44%	47%	50%	56%
OT36	5%	4%	4%	6%	18%	17%	23%	32%	38%	43%	50%	54%	63%
OT37	5%	4%	4%	7%	13%	16%	23%	33%	39%	44%	50%	54%	63%
OT38	4%	4%	5%	6%	16%	21%	25%	32%	35%	41%	55%	62%	65%
MO01	3%	3%	4%	6%	19%	19%	24%	31%	42%	48%	51%	58%	66%

Table 6: SRI scoring impacts on P4P plans

4.3 Analysis

4.3.1 Model building scenarios

Naturally, SBT groups consisting of fewer methods generally have a lower scoring impact than measures comprised of a greater variety – aiming to gain more of the potential of low hanging fruits for gains. Noticeably though, the impact generally increases with the number of affected domains. This is due to the computation structure of the SRI score as a weighted average of the domain sub scores.

As a result, the domain-specific groups for ventilation, lighting, DHW and the building envelope all score between impact ratings of 3-6 %. SBT groups that influence multiple domains score significantly higher at least 19 % for adaptive systems and cooperation models – the SRI focuses on high-profile functions and gains.

Higher scores require active coordination between base-level subsystems through dedicated systems like BEMS (24 %) or BACS (31 %) as ‘bus systems’ within a building providing a middleware. Since rudimentary domain-specific subsystems have to be installed and made interoperable to the overarching system, these measures come with higher requirements in expertise for installation, configuration and workload as well. BEMS benefit greatly from the involvement of heat efficient technologies and a greater domain interlock, doubling the score to 48 %. Due to the high average consumption share of the heating domain, the partially energy-balanced SRI rewards an efficient heating management especially high. A close domain interlock allows the BEMS to realize the energy re-distribution and storing to its greatest extent.

The participation in smart building communities a P4P program can facilitate enables a BACS to utilize the data collected by its peers, and offer its DR capabilities. This is reflected by an SRI impact score increase to 51 %.

Both BACS and BEMS can take advantage of adaptive systems for controllable consumption devices, leading to overall impact scores of 48 % and 58 % respectively. As before, the BACS stays slightly ahead of the BEMS in terms of SRI impact scoring. Combining these systems and fully developing their subsystems yields the greatest score increase at 66 %, if the challenges in interoperability and workload can be overcome.

4.3.2 Pilot building scenarios

The pilot buildings exhibit remarkable scoring symmetry to each other and the model building. This further validates the above conclusions, and demonstrates a general applicability of the best performing control solutions.

The most impactful technology groups are consistently built around a high level BACS/ BEMS and can be updated in several steps by connecting ever more subsystems. For several pilot buildings, rudimentary domain sub-systems governed by an adaptive BACS/ BEMS that facilitates the participation in Smart Building communities already bring the building very close to its maximal achievable SRI value. Only two of the penitentiary centres are outliers to this rule, as their comfort related subsystems are of higher significance than in non-residential buildings.

A noticeable asymmetry across the building types is the scoring imbalance between a participation in cooperation models and the installation of adaptive systems for controllable consumption devices. While evenly matched for the simulated model building, CU02, ED60 and OF39 strongly prefer the latter. The opposite is true for OF27, OF40 and OT38. In general, buildings with strict requirements to their conditioning have reduced capability to participate in communal energy balancing, and benefit more from advanced systems for their specific equipment. For the same reason, BACSs also prove considerably more effective than BEMSs for the first group of buildings.

The single-domain improvements, particularly the DHW management system, show their greatest potential for buildings with high occupancy profiles and large scale distribution infrastructure (OT36, OT37, OT38). The consumption associated to the DHW and ventilation domains take up above average shares of the energy cost for residential buildings and increase the scoring share of these domains accordingly.

4.4 Recommendations from the technological point of view

The SRI impact results for the model building clearly favour high level control systems that coordinate the functions of various domain-specific subsystems.

Management solutions like a BACS or a BEMS are highly recommendable extensions iff the program or the participating building already takes advantage of semi-automated control systems for specific installations and equipment. The return value of a BACS/ BEMS scales with the number and sophistication of administered subsystems. Merging all subsystems under a common interface does however pose a considerable challenge. External contractors of these growing markets could provide the necessary expertise to the program facilitator and the building managers. For programs with low automation or short duration and buildings of small size the interoperability and integration costs of these systems might exceed their value. Such programs are better served with low return but low effort measures such as upgrades to the lighting, DHW or ventilation system. Window control system installations often require a complete window replacement and are thus only cost-effective if these replacements were already overdue.

The SENSEI P4P programs are set to incorporate EE aggregators for the sharing and evaluation of building data and EEM plans between building owners, as well as the identification of opportunities for participation in energy saving portfolios. Many market-oriented portfolios will only be applicable to buildings with advanced control systems. BACSs in particular empower the building owner to greatly benefit from the shared information and facilitate energy service developments (e.g., ESCOs, EPC-contracts). Programs aiming to achieve large scale Smart Grid integration and DSM for deep energy retrofits will come to rely on BEMSs. Especially in combination with controllable equipment, owners can profit from DR Service tariffs and a reliable demand prediction. Energy savings accumulated by EE improvements could be stored by a TES for later release during peak times. Such services will however require a robust legal framework, as there are strict guidelines to follow for the EU market.

BACS and BEMS intersect in their services to an extent. When installing both separately, their cumulative value is reduced by this redundancy. Optimally, both functionalities would be incorporated into a single system, raising complexity but reducing maintenance effort. The feasibility of these Software improvements of course also depends on the program budget and duration, as the accompanying Hardware upgrades are a steadily increasing cost factor, and systematic improvements accumulate their effect mostly in the long term. This leaves an

opportunity for third party investments, data sharing with big data collectors, or participation in social policies (e.g., addressing regional energy poverty).

5 Implementation of Technologies

With the original SRI technology catalogue as listed below, the aim was to find out standardization gaps and need for alignment just like in the M/490 mandate of the EC to various SDOs⁴.

Standards can contribute to the development of an SRI by assisting in identifying or quantifying functionalities and services in a fast and harmonized way.

The ‘smart ready services’ in the SRI study were to a large extent sourced from standards. This is especially the case for many of the services sourced from EN 15232 ‘Energy performance of buildings - Impact of Building Automation, Controls and Building Management’ (module M10). This standard is the overarching standard that models the impact of Building Automation and Controls Systems (BACS) on the energy consumption of the building. It is used within EPBD and contains a structured list of BACS and Technical Building Management (TBM) functions. Other examples include the lighting control systems as defined in EN 15193-1:2017, Smart Grid Use cases from IEC 62559-2:2015, etc.

5.1 Standards

The most important standards which will be covering the Smart Services are covered in the Annex D of the preparatory study for the SRI. Still, there are open issues with the indicator on emerging functionality. Standards evolve over the time as does the state-of-the-art. Other domains proved that indicators vary over the time since technologies become more common and lead to better aggregated services which provide more benefit to the user. Thus, the TRL changes as a smart building becomes less smart compared to newer ones. Therefore, the list of standards shall be constantly evaluated as readiness changes over the time. This is particularly true for the system which are closely related to more Software oriented solutions as the run-time platforms provide the infrastructure for those systems to be deployed.

⁴ Verbeke S., Waide P., Bettgenhäuser K., Uslar M., Bogaert S. et al.; “Support for setting up a Smart Readiness Indicator for buildings and related impact assessment - final report”; August 2018; Brussels

5.2 Services

Services evolve and build upon over the course of the time. TRLs are not consistently with equal distance of invest between the various domains in the SRI and thus, it is always a case-to-case decision if a service is really improving all needed dimensions of the project for a building. It might just improve the Readiness but might not be super cost efficient in the end compared to other measures. So, in addition to the SRI, CBA and technology readiness concepts are needed when taking economic decisions.

5.3 Data models

One important aspect of the readiness is the technological side of investments. The semantics of the services involved often do not change rapidly over time, however, communication stacks do. The data and information used in context shall be based on standardized semantics and data models. As for the building domain, wide-spread and used ontologies like SAREF⁵ with its various extension have emerged.

6 Conclusion

Within this deliverable on SENSEI, a compiled stack of possible and useful Smart Services (and technologies) was presented in context. One has to distinguish between so called Hardware and Software technology stacks. The technologies stem from a desk research conducted in SENSEI. Their characteristics were described, and put in context with the building types in SENSEI and put into simulation. Thus, contributions of “technology packages” for building for P4P were evaluated and conclusions drawn. These conclusions put an emphasis on certain combinations of stacks which provide better revenue and smartness than others.

7 References

[1] <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1364032119308688#bib6>

⁵ <https://saref.etsi.org/>

[2] <https://blogs.bsria.co.uk/2020/03/18/the-european-bacs-market-looking-up/>

[3] <https://www.mordorintelligence.com/industry-reports/building-energy-management-systems-in-europe-industry>

[4] <https://www.techsciresearch.com/report/indoor-air-quality-monitor-market/2815.html>

[5] <https://www.gminsights.com/industry-analysis/window-automation-market>

[6] <https://www.graphicalresearch.com/industry-insights/1023/europe-smart-lighting-market>

8 Supplemental material and appendix

In addition to this document summarizing the results in table 6, the Excel spreadsheets used can be found on Zenodo under the title “SENSEI D8.2 Pilot Assessment Calculations” <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6127655>